

ADJUSTING EARNINGS BEFORE INTERESTS, TAX DEPRECIATION AND AMORTIZATION : WHEN AND HOW ?

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Abstract

EBITDA is often used as a measure of a company's ability to generate cash. EBITDA takes into account the income and expenses incurred by the company's day-to-day operations and is readily available in a company's financial statements. On the other hand, the EBITDA of a company cannot be used as a benchmark unless it has been standardized through adjustments. These restatements include, for example, variations in production, payment of rent and personnel, taxes, changes in working capital, or extraordinary expenses that may have unusually affected a company's performance over an accounting period. The purpose of this article is to analyze in which context the adjusted EBITDA can be used, how it can be reported and what are the possible adjustments. This will be done through three case studies:

- A company operating in the service industry (e.g.: hotel and catering)
- A company selling professional equipment (e.g.: plumbing)
- A company acquiring another company

INTRODUCTION

The content and frequency of reporting will vary based on the revenues of the company, the nature of investors and the industry the business operates in. However, the EBITDA is often required in any reporting regardless of the size and the maturity of the business. The EBITDA is obtained by subtracting the cost of goods sold and selling, general and administrative expenses to the total revenues of the companies. As such, EBITDA does not take into account taxes, interests, depreciation and amortization as its acronym indicates. EBITDA includes only costs and revenues that are linked to the main operations of the business and excludes revenues and costs that are non-recurring or linked to the financing of the business.

EBITDA is required in most reporting since it is the nearest approximation of cash flows, though; it ignores many factors that affect the true cash flows, such as debt payments. EBITDA could be helpful to evaluate corporations in the same industry with widely different capital structures, tax rates, and depreciation and amortization policies. If financial professionals review the reporting, chances are the EBITDA would be used to calculate financial ratios of profitability (P/E ratio), solvency (leverage ratio) or any other relevant metric. Many covenants drawn out in the financing legal documentation would be based on EBITDA. The Enterprise Value is regularly determined as a multiple of EBITDA so that the price can be benchmarked against other companies in the sector. Therefore, EBITDA is a metric that entrepreneurs should keep an eye on throughout the life of the business. However, it's a non-IFRS or US GAAP metric.

Still, the supremacy of EBITDA remains contested for several reasons. First, it is not suitable for every industry. Indeed, in industries where the fixed capital investment is consequent, the depreciation should be included in the financial metric considered. The EBITDA of a retail company owning a lot of Real Estate would not show the store maintenance expenses that are a non-negligible part of its operations. If an analyst does not consider this cost in its analysis, it is missing out on a large cash outflow. The company might have a very high EBITDA but might be decapitalizing itself in the long term. Second, the EBITDA can be easily manipulated through a depreciation policy. As such, a company can record important expenses as an asset and depreciate it over the years rather than record an operating expense to maintain an acceptable EBITDA (Berman & Knight, 2009).

1. Uses of Adjusted EBITDA

Adjusted EBITDA differs from the standard EBITDA measure in that a company's adjusted EBITDA is used to normalize its income and expenses.

Standardizing EBITDA by removing anomalies means the resulting adjusted or normalized EBITDA is more accurately and easily comparable the EBITDA of other companies. Adjusted EBITDA, as opposed to the non-adjusted version, will attempt to eliminate idiosyncrasies, which makes it easier to compare multiple business units or companies in a given industry. The adjusted EBITDA measurement removes non-recurring, irregular and one-time items that may distort EBITDA.

One example is the case of the French Prime Macron, which made more than one accountant scratch their heads. Indeed, in many instances, companies had to account the Prime Macron within the labor costs, therefore reducing the EBITDA. If a French company were to be compared with a UK company of the same industry, all things being equal, the French company would appear less competitive due to this expense and would have a lower valuation on the EV/EBITDA scale. However, the Prime Macron is a one-time labor cost expense and this lower EBITDA is not representative of an actual loss of performance. That's where adjustment comes into play: the adjusted EBITDA would not record this Prime since it is a non-recurring expense (PWC, 2019).

While there is a broad consensus as to what is an EBITDA, there is no precise definition of what should be a proper adjusted EBITDA. Adjusted EBITDA is however broadly mentioned in many corporate finance manuals (e.g. Vernimmen) since it is used in financial modeling to calculate the Enterprise Value through Discounted Cash Flows. Financial professionals networks release valuation guidelines for best practices and intend to give a broad definition of what constitutes a reasonable adjustment (e.g. IPEV guidelines). Adjusted EBITDA can also be described as “maintainable earnings”, “sustainable earnings”, “restated EBITDA” or “normalized EBITDA”. Besides, the adjustments are not audited in the public financial statements but can be checked and certified by audit and accounting firms upon investors' requests (e.g. covenants compliance certificates).

The lack of definition of adjusted EBITDA and the incentive to show a high level of cash generation have triggered the invention of many interesting adjustments. Private Equity International published a tribune in June 2019 called *Ebitda on steroids* (Thomson, 2019). This tribune found echo among the investors' community since it was describing the experience of financial professionals working with SMEs. The article gave examples of EBITDA adjustments such as “add-backs based on any and all Brexit-related costs and losses of sales” (Thomson, 2019). Aware of the proliferation of EBITDA adjustments, banks have incorporated a limitation on the level of adjustments accepted from the portfolio companies to finance investment funds and SMEs themselves.

While adjustments are a good way to correct EBITDA's flaws, it is also subject to many misuses. The next section would strive to find common grounds on what constitutes acceptable adjustments.

2. Definition of adjusted EBITDA (Canis, 2017)

Proposed definition:

Adjusted EBITDA is a financial metric taking into account all operating revenues and expenses of the company. It is computed by adding or subtracting to the EBITDA any non-recurring, any cash operating elements and any company or context-specific elements that bias the view of the financial performance of the business and hinders comparability.

Based on that definition, we can now define the main categories and elements that constitute reasonable adjustments. These categories are based on notes posted by practitioners.

2.1. Non- recurring expenses

The most common expenses belonging to the category of non – recurring expenses are legal fees linked to a one-time event such as litigation or the constitution of a new legal entity. It may also include expenses incurred in the frame of a restructuring or a sale of an asset. It can be more unfortunate events such as fire or theft losses. It may include also any regular expenses that are higher or lower than usual and that should be adjusted to reflect the standard level of financial performance.

2.2. Cash operating items

Some operating expenses may be in the cash flow statement but are not recorded in the EBITDA. While expenses incurred in renewing the current assets are usually accounted as CAPEX, the classification is not straightforward. For instance, a firm may need to develop its machinery to deliver a single offer that may be used for further orders. According to whether the expense is incurred for one or several demands, it would change the recording of the expense and may need to be adjusted in the EBITDA.

2.3. Company-specific elements

Generally part of the Selling, General and Administrative expenses, the rents shall be adjusted to standardize the EBITDA. Indeed, some companies may be paying rent above or under market practices. To reflect an accurate financial performance, an add-back or subtraction should be made to align the prices.

Salaries, in particular Management remuneration, must be normalized both upwards and downwards.

2.4. Context specific elements

2.4.1. Accounting policies

While IFRS and US GAAP govern most of our audited financial reports nowadays, there may be many contexts where these standards are not applicable or not applied. Hence, some expenses may be included in the EBITDA items in some countries while the majority of countries have another accounting treatment. For instance, leasing contracts are now accounted as financial expenses under IFRS 16 and are hence generally excluded from the EBITDA, which may not be followed by all accounting departments.

2.4.2. Regulations

When analyzing a foreign firm, it may be important to take into account the regulation and the specificities of the countries. For instance, some countries may have specific taxes or subsidies that may be important to know and adjust to having a better view of the firm's performance. A French example would be the Crédit Impôt recherche, which is a temporary curb on taxes computed on the R&D of French SMEs. Therefore it can represent a subsidy for

many firms who have a negative profit since they receive money from the government through this tax scheme.

3. Case studies

3.1. Case 1

The Company started in 2013 and has a 6 years track record. It operates in the catering industry where sales are on a contract per contract basis. The main expenses are the waiters and organization staff. It does not provide the food but only the staff. It has recurring clients: parliament, companies' event department, restaurants,...

Figure N°1 : Sample revenues and expenses report of a catering company

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Revenues	230.000	270.000	360.000	440.000	450.000	460.000	410.000
Parliament	90.000	90.000	90.000	90.000	90.000	90.000	90.000
Parliament revenues	90.000						
Company 1	60.000	60.000	60.000	60.000	60.000	60.000	
Company 2			50.000	50.000	50.000		
Company 3						50.000	50.000
Company 4					50.000	50.000	50.000
Company 5				40.000	40.000	50.000	50.000
Company revenues	60.000	60.000	110.000	150.000	200.000	210.000	150.000
Restaurant 1	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000		40.000
Restaurant 2	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000		40.000	40.000
Restaurant 3		40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000
Restaurant 4			40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000	40.000
Restaurant 5				40.000	40.000	40.000	10.000
Restaurant revenues	80.000	120.000	160.000	200.000	160.000	160.000	170.000
COGS	200.000	250.000	325.000	350.000	350.000	450.000	400.000
Staff	200.000	250.000	325.000	350.000	350.000	450.000	400.000
N° of waiters	2	4	7	8	8	8	8
N° of managers	3	3	3	3	3	4	4
Gross margin	30.000	20.000	35.000	90.000	100.000	10.000	10.000
	13%	7%	10%	20%	22%	2%	2%
SG&A	10.000	10.000	10.000	10.000	30.000	10.000	10.000
Marketing costs	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	25.000	5.000	5.000
Administrative	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000	5.000
EBITDA	20.000	10.000	25.000	80.000	70.000	-	-
	9%	4%	7%	18%	16%	0%	0%
VERSION A							
Ajustment - Company 1							60.000
Ajustment - Company 2						50.000	50.000
Ajustment - Restaurant 1						40.000	
Ajustment - Restaurant 2					40.000		
Ajustment - Restaurant 5							30.000
Ajustment Marketing					20.000		
Ajustment Staff						50.000	
Total adjustments	-	-	-	-	60.000	140.000	140.000
Normalized EBITDA	20.000	10.000	25.000	80.000	130.000	140.000	140.000
<i>Normalized EBITDA margin</i>	9%	4%	7%	18%	29%	30%	34%

- Adjustments on revenues: the adjustment on Company 1,2 and Restaurant 1,2 and 5 are adjustments meant to compensate the fact that some clients did not choose to use their contract some years but that it does not correspond to a sustainable loss of these clients. While this seems reasonable for Company 1 as well as for Restaurants 1 and 2, this does not seem reasonable for Company 2 and Restaurants 5. Indeed, for Company 1, the client has not been ordering for 2 consecutive years and this client was acquired recently. With the same reasoning, the client Restaurant 5 had been acquired recently and ordered for three years consecutively, which may not be proof of a permanent order for such a recent SME. However, a review of the legal contracts may help justify these adjustments: if Restaurant 5 was committed to ordering for a total of 200,000€ over 5 years, chances are the revenue is predictable over the next year and the adjustment is justified. Overall, adjustments to revenues are generally not acceptable.
- Adjustment on marketing costs: in 2017, the company incurred additional marketing costs to develop its brand name. This is a typical example of reasonable adjustments since the marketing expenses were stable before and it's a one-time expense needed to expand the customer base.
- Adjustment on labor costs: a bonus was paid to one of the new managers to hire him. However, this bonus was paid because the salaries paid to managers are inferior to that of the market. Hence, the bonus should not be added back, but rather, the salaries of other managers should be aligned every year.

Figure N°2 : EBITDA adjustment of a catering company

EBITDA	20.000	10.000	25.000	80.000	70.000	45.000	-
	9%	4%	7%	18%	16%	10%	0%
VERSION B							
Ajustment - Company 1							
Ajustment - Company 2							
Ajustment - Restaurant 1							
Ajustment - Restaurant 2							
Ajustment - Restaurant 5							
Ajustment Marketing					20.000		
Ajustment Staff	- 15.000	- 15.000	- 15.000	- 15.000	- 15.000	- 15.000	- 20.000
Total adjustments	15.000	15.000	15.000	15.000	5.000	15.000	20.000
Normalized EBITDA	5.000	5.000	10.000	65.000	75.000	30.000	20.000
<i>Normalized EBITDA margin</i>	2%	-2%	3%	15%	17%	7%	-5%

This gives a different evolution. On the one hand, the initial version (Version A) of normalized EBITDA shows earnings trending up with a level of normalized EBITDA of 140,000€ in 2019 (140% superior to the actual EBITDA!). On the other hand, the corrected version (Version B) shows an EBITDA increasing from 2014 to 2017 and a recent downside trend, with a normalized EBITDA of 40,000€ in 2019. These discrepancies are more obvious when plotting a graph of the year on year evolution.

Figure N°3: Graph of adjusted and unadjusted EBITDA (Version A)

Figure N°4: Graph of adjusted and unadjusted EBITDA (Version B)

3.2. Case 2

The Company started in 2012 and sells plumbing material. It also offers tube-mounting services. It is remunerated upon delivery of materials and/or upon completion of milestones in the tube-mounting projects.

Figure N°5 : Sample revenues and expenses report of a plumbing company

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Revenues	500.000	535.000	572.450	601.073	631.126	662.682	728.951
Beginning inventory	60.000	65.000	32.000	75.000	10.000	30.000	40.000
+ Total purchase costs	300.000	320.000	342.400	359.520	410.000	450.000	500.000
- Purchase discounts	-	10.000	-	-	-	-	-
- Purchase returns and allowance	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
- End inventory	70.000	30.000	70.000	10.000	30.000	40.000	30.000
Cost of Goods Sold	- 290.000	- 345.000	- 304.400	- 424.520	- 390.000	- 440.000	- 510.000
<i>Cost of inventory used/sales</i>	<i>58%</i>	<i>64%</i>	<i>53%</i>	<i>71%</i>	<i>62%</i>	<i>66%</i>	<i>70%</i>
<i>Days in inventories</i>	<i>88</i>	<i>32</i>	<i>84</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>28</i>	<i>33</i>	<i>21</i>
Gross Margin	210.000	190.000	268.050	176.553	241.126	222.682	218.951
<i>Margin</i>	<i>42%</i>	<i>36%</i>	<i>47%</i>	<i>29%</i>	<i>38%</i>	<i>34%</i>	<i>30%</i>
Rent	- 30.000	- 30.000	- 30.000	- 30.000	- 30.000	- 30.000	- 30.000
Staff	- 20.000	- 20.000	- 20.000	- 20.000	- 30.000	- 30.000	- 30.000
Administrative costs	- 5.000	- 5.000	- 5.000	- 5.000	- 5.000	- 5.000	- 5.000
EBITDA	155.000	135.000	213.050	121.553	176.126	157.682	153.951
<i>Margin</i>	<i>31%</i>	<i>25%</i>	<i>37%</i>	<i>20%</i>	<i>28%</i>	<i>24%</i>	<i>21%</i>

The cost of goods sold is composed of the beginning inventory + net purchases – end inventory. When calculating the ratio of the cost of inventory used on sales we notice that the maximum ratios are in 2016 and 2019, standing at 71% and 70%. However, it seems that in 2016, the ratio Days in Inventory was the smallest of all time. How can we explain that and can we adjust it?

- Supplier's bargaining power: In 2016, the company used a lot of its stock in inventory rather than new purchases (beginning inventory – end inventory = 60). The new purchases were relatively cheap compared to the inventories since the stock in inventory was overpriced due to suppliers' pricing 2014 and 2015 years. Typically, this results from a low bargaining power with providers or bad stock management and shall not be adjusted since it refers to the productive and financial performance of the Company.
- One-time supply overpricing: In 2018, the supplier was low on stocks and the company had to buy more expensive items than usual to service its regular orders. The

company could not change provider by the time it was informed of the supply shortage. This triggered a +20,000€ the order. Since the company is not responsible for this, it should not impact the performance and a +20,000€ adjustment can be made.

- Lower gross margin to service one specific order: A customer has made a special request requiring a more expensive inventory to service him. The service was priced higher, however, the gross margin on this client was lower than on the average client thus dropping the overall margin (i.e: revenues of 150,000€ and purchase of 112,500€, leaving a gross margin of 25% on this client), no adjustment shall be made to even out the gross margin since it is part of the operations of the business to service the client.

More generally, an adjustment can be made to smooth out the distribution of the stock production to the revenues. Indeed, all purchases in year N are not meant to be sold during year N and there may be a cut-off issue between year N and N+1.

For instance, in 2013 the company ordered 50,000€ of pipes for a project spanning from October 2013 to April 2014, paid by the client upon some milestones. This can lead to a wide variety of evaluations at the end of December 2013 and can be done through the percentage of delivery completed or the percentage of hours completed on the project.

3.3. Case 3

Company A has operated for 10 years and acquires Company B. Company B will move its operations to the office of Company A and the labor force would be merged.

Figure N°6: Sample revenues and expenses report of an acquiring and acquired company

Company A		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Revenues		1,000,000	1,050,000	1,102,500	1,157,625	1,215,506	1,276,282	1,340,096
Cost of Goods Sold	-	430,000	454,000	479,000	505,000	533,000	562,000	593,000
Gross Margin		570,000	596,000	623,500	652,625	682,506	714,282	747,096
Margin		57%	57%	57%	56%	56%	56%	56%
Rent	-	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	190,000
Staff	-	50,000	55,000	55,000	60,000	65,000	80,000	200,000
Administrative costs	-	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000
Others	-	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000
EBITDA		390,000	411,000	438,500	462,625	487,506	504,282	327,096
Margin		39%	39%	40%	40%	40%	40%	24%
Company B		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Revenues		300,000	360,000	432,000	518,400	622,080	746,496	
Cost of Goods Sold	-	130,000	156,000	187,200	224,640	269,568	323,482	
Gross Margin		170,000	204,000	244,800	293,760	352,512	423,014	
Margin		57%	57%	57%	57%	57%	57%	
Rent	-	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	
Staff	-	30,000	30,000	35,000	40,000	45,000	55,000	
Administrative costs	-	7,000	17,000	27,000	37,000	47,000	57,000	
Others	-	5,000	15,000	25,000	35,000	45,000	55,000	
EBITDA		28,000	42,000	57,800	81,760	115,512	156,014	
Margin		9%	12%	13%	16%	19%	21%	

- Adjustment on past revenues (Pro Forma): these sorts of adjustments are generally admitted and even required by most financial analysts as they want to be able to compare past performances with the current performance of the company. As we can see, the Pro Forma revenues from 2013 to 2018 are cumulative of both companies and help to see whether the acquisition has improved the gross margin and the EBITDA margin.
- Adjustment on integration costs: when merging companies, there is often a double counting of expenses (double office spaces, double staffing) that does not represent the long term operating performance of companies.

Figure N°7: Pro Forma EBITDA adjustments

Pro Forma	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Revenues	1,300,000	1,410,000	1,534,500	1,676,025	1,837,586	2,022,778	1,340,096
Cost of Goods Sold	- 560,000	- 610,000	- 666,200	- 729,640	- 802,568	- 885,482	593,000
Gross Margin	740,000	800,000	868,300	946,385	1,035,018	1,137,296	747,096
Margin	57%	57%	57%	56%	56%	56%	56%
Rent	- 100,000	- 100,000	- 100,000	- 100,000	- 100,000	- 100,000	190,000
Staff	- 80,000	- 85,000	- 90,000	- 100,000	- 110,000	- 135,000	135,000
Administrative costs	- 27,000	- 37,000	- 47,000	- 57,000	- 67,000	- 77,000	20,000
Others	- 15,000	- 25,000	- 35,000	- 45,000	- 55,000	- 65,000	10,000
EBITDA	518,000	553,000	596,300	644,385	703,018	760,296	392,096
Margin	40%	39%	39%	38%	38%	38%	29%
Adjustment integration Company B - Rent							90,000
Adjustment integration Company B - Staff							30,000
Normalized EBITDA	518,000	553,000	596,300	644,385	703,018	760,296	512,096
Normalized EBITDA margin	40%	39%	39%	38%	38%	38%	38%

CONCLUSION

Adjustments can be made on a range of financial metrics: debt level, EBIT, etc. However, they shall be used with caution:

1. Discuss with the end-user of the financial statements to assess the reasonableness and the validity of the adjustments: the EBITDA and the adjusted EBITDA are non-GAAP metrics, subject to a lot of subjectivity in the computation.
2. Moderation is key: the adjusted EBITDA should not be significantly higher than the actual EBITDA. Banks started to set thresholds concerning the level of acceptable adjustments, usually set around 20% and 30%.
3. Track record is key: a young company should have fewer adjustments since it has fewer track records to assess a sustainable level of performance.
4. Adjustments are not meant to inflate the financial performance.
5. Graphs can help: as identified in Case 1, graphs can help identify the acceptable level of EBITDA adjustments.

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